

Awareness, Attitude and Adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies in Lagos State

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Abstract

The global advertising industry, has been infiltrated by digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), and has seen several applications. This chapter investigates the awareness, attitude, and adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) for content creation within advertising agencies in Lagos State using the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) Model and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The study used a mixed-methods approach incorporating qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys with 10 management staff and 61 creatives within the agencies. Total enumeration of all creatives was done and the study recorded a 100% response rate. Cronbach's Alpha reliability ranges from 0.723 to 0.868. Findings revealed that awareness of AI positively influenced attitude towards AI for content creation ($R^2=0.244$). Awareness of AI was revealed to not significantly influence the adoption of AI tools in advertising agencies ($R^2=0.008$). It was concluded that although attitudes towards AI for content creation were positive, extent of adoption remains low, hindered by challenges such as data privacy concerns, budget constraints, and compatibility issues. The study recommended targeted awareness initiatives and strategic interventions to overcome adoption barriers and foster innovation within the advertising industry.

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INTRODUCTION

In advertising, content creation is where messages for communication collide with ideas tied together creatively in order to appeal to the selected target audience. As technology continues to advance, today's consumer is also constantly evolving and becoming more sophisticated in their wants and as such personalization in advertising has skyrocketed in order to cater for diverse audience preferences and increase the appeal and relevance of advertisements to the audience. Chandra et al. (2022), stated that personalization is the design and production of communication messages in alignment with customer preferences. The study further confirms that personalization of marketing communication is a rising trend in the marketing landscape. Consequently, traditional content creation within advertising agencies may not be best suited to address this new market dynamic as traditional methods of content creation could be resource intensive and time consuming. However, the use of artificial intelligence in content creation could bridge this need gap by using the different audience interests and preferences collected through tracking algorithm to create engaging and informative advertisements that could capture audience interest.

However, as affirmed by Nwachukwu and Affen (2023), it seems that its adoption in the Nigerian Advertising Industry has been limited. Addressing the challenges revolving around AI in the advertising industry is quintessential in opening up the possibilities that abound with AI in this creative industry. One of the likely challenges is that creatives in advertising agencies may lack awareness of the specific AI features and tools that could be applied to content creation and therefore be unable to exploit AI potential in advertising. Furthermore, the attitude of creatives towards AI in content creation as regards to their perception of it, their reluctance or skepticism associated with the use of AI could cause stagnation and lack of technological advancement in the industry.

Similarly, there is the need to address the challenges that creatives may likely encounter in the adoption of AI in content creation ranging the organizational culture, cost, ethical concerns, etc. Leaving these unaddressed, renders a significant challenge as it not only limits the growth of innovation within the industry but it also creates an urgent need for the Nigerian Advertising industry to be at par with international counterparts and explore the range of possibilities that Artificial Intelligence presents, leading to enhanced content creation in advertising and fulfilling the evolving needs of today's consumer.

Objectives of the Study

1. find out the level of awareness that management staff and creatives of advertising agencies in Lagos State have about AI for content creation;
2. investigate the attitude of management staff and creatives of advertising agencies in Lagos State towards using AI for content creation;
3. examine the extent of adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State;
4. explore the challenges encountered in the adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos state.

Test of Hypotheses

H01: Awareness of AI for content creation does not significantly influence attitude towards AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State.

H02: Awareness of AI for content creation does not significantly influence adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State.

Literature Review

Overview of Content Creation

Content creation is the bane of all advertisements regardless of the medium used in dissemination. Content creation is the process of generating ideas and the communication of identified messages through meaningful symbols to a target audience. It is the strategic and creative process of developing various forms of media to communicate messages to a target audience. According to Gerzic and Abou Osman, (2017) content is represented by any photos, videos, visual material, storytelling material and written material that has been thought out and structured in advance of its creation.

The significance of content creation in advertising cannot be emphasized, it performs various

functions in helping a brand communicate as well as attain set marketing objectives. Gerzic and Abou Osman (2017) incorporated insights from Gangdon (2014). The study identifies three major functions of content in advertising. Firstly, it serves to disseminate information about a firm, encompassing details about their processes, skills, and offered products or services. Subsequently, it is tailored to address the audience's needs, illustrating how the firm can provide solutions and fulfill those needs. Moreover, content contributes to establishing a competitive advantage, positioning the firm as the most desirable among competitors. Yang et al., (2019), concluded that content creation is able to evoke emotions in consumers making them resonate with the brand and inadvertently shaping their purchase behaviors.

Artificial Intelligence as a Content Creation Tool

Artificial intelligence, according to Sheikh et al., (2023) are “systems that display intelligent behavior by analyzing their environment and taking actions with some degree of autonomy to achieve specific goals”. This definition encompasses the characteristics of artificial intelligence as a technology that relies on data derived from machine learning in order to efficiently replicate human intellectual capabilities. Therefore, Artificial intelligence as a content creation tool is the use of intelligent systems to replicate human creativity in the development of advertising content which would be broadly classified into three (3) elements in this study.

Elements of Content Creation

The effectiveness of an advertisement is a function of what is said and how it is said (Patrick and Hagtvedt, 2011). An effective advertisement is created through several creative elements which can be majorly grouped into the copy, audio, visual elements.

Copywriting as an Element of Content Creation

Copywriting is arguably the most important aspect of content creation as it forms the foundation of most advertisements regardless of the medium through which it is disseminated. Zia et al., (2018) states that copywriting is the language of advertising and it is not medium limited, as just as radio advertisements are built on the foundation of a written script so are television and print advertisements. According to Albrighton (2013), in his book *The ABC of copywriting*, he defines copywriting as the optimum use of language to promote or persuade. This denotes that copywriting is the use of the right tone, right words, right voice, right length, and right structure to communicate promotional or persuasive messages to a consumer.

Traditional copywriting faces some challenges according to findings from the study by Shamsuddin et al., (2023), which implementing AI can bridge such as creative restrictions, limitations to knowledge of cultural values, time-consuming processes, cost of having multiple copywriters on payroll especially for small sized agencies. AI-tools can create engaging copies in seconds and target it to different audience demographics and segments using AI tracking algorithm.

Audio Generation as an Element of Content Creation

Audio content has evolved from just being for radio advertisements, so there is the need for diversifying and personalizing content. Audio advertisements are placed not only on radio but also music streaming sites, podcasts, and even outdoor advertising. The need for audio content goes beyond personalization and on the go advertising, it ensures that certain user groups are catered for by providing accessibility to consumers with cognitive disabilities such as dyslexia, hearing loss, loss of eyesight, etc. Arias-Badia and Matamala (2020) inferred that in order to allow visually impaired consumers to fully experience the form and content of the work of art or media, verbal

descriptions of the content are given. These components usually include at least where and when the action takes place (spatio-temporal settings), who is involved (characters), and what is happening (action).

Traditional audio content generation could be daunting and resource intensive and have limited opportunities for customization especially for bridging the language gap existing in the translation of foreign content to local content. Artificial Intelligence offers several capabilities such as voice synthesis, tone modulation, and dynamic sound profile generation that may be difficult or nearly unattainable with solely traditional methods. The possibilities of AI in audio content creation according to Rehm (2020), include Transcription of audio for subtitling, speech generation. Other uses in AI audio generation which have emerged with recent advancements include; Speaker classification, Emotion recognition, Scene detection, Detection of illegal content, Detection of deep fakes.

Visual Generation as an Element of Content Creation

Visual elements play a fundamental role in content creation and communicating a brand's messages to consumers. Visual symbols are put together in order to express ideas with the target audience. Visual properties in an advertisement including; images, graphics, posters, videos, visual art, contribute significantly to grabbing and retaining interest. A product's personality can be developed through the use of visual imagery, which can also be used to draw in customers, pique their curiosity, highlight features and benefits, and solidify a brand's identity in the eyes of target consumers (Patrick and Hagtvedt, 2011). Shehata et al., (2020), reported the use of visual symbols in an advertisement makes it stand out and appeal to their target audience.

The creation of visual content typically involves the creative work of the art director, videographer, graphic designer, illustrator and other creatives. Chan-Olmsted (2019) affirmed that creating,

editing and refining visual content for use in advertisements could be exhausting and difficult to target visual content to different audience segments in order to maximize efficiency. AI has a wide range of applications in the creation of visual content. Ivanov (2023) confirms that through the analysis of visual patterns made possible by machine learning algorithms, a variety of visuals that are contextually relevant can be easily created. AI-driven design tools also help accelerate the creative process by providing solutions for everything from color selection to page layout design.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) Model

The TAM (Davis, 1989) posits that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness would precede the acceptance of information technology. In the same vein, if creatives of advertising agencies in Lagos State perceive AI easy to use for content creation and to be useful in their creative work, they would be more open to adopting it.

Fig. 1 illustrates the technology acceptance model of AI in content creation by advertising agencies in Lagos State.

Figure 1 Adapted from Technology Acceptance Model

Essentially, S-O-R Model (Mehrabian and Russell, 1974), stipulates that the behavior of people is influenced by their response to external stimuli. This denotes that, the availability of AI-tools for content creation, organizational policies, cost of implementation, affects the internal reactions of the management and creative staff , these internal factors include their knowledge of AI features for content creation, their attitude towards AI for content creation and prior experience or usage of AI in content creation. The effect of the external stimuli on the organism would then cause a behavioral response which in this case, could be the adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies.

Fig. 2 shows the sequence of S-O-R in management staff and creatives of advertising agencies in Lagos state.

Figure 2 Adapted from S-O-R Model

Methodology

This study adopted a convergent parallel mixed methods research design, in which total enumeration of the population was carried out. The population comprised sixty-one (61) creatives found in ten (10) agencies in Lagos state and one (1) management staff each for the in-depth interviews.

3.2 Reliability

Table 1 indicates the Cronbach's alpha reliability result of the constructs, which shows that all the Cronbach's alpha scores of the constructs were greater than 0.7 which is the benchmark; therefore, the constructs had internal consistency.

Table 1
Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test
Table 3.7.1 Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test Result

Constructs	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Awareness of AI for Content Creation	9	0.727
Attitude towards AI for Content Creation	12	0.723
Adoption of AI for Content Creation	9	0.868
Challenges facing the adoption of AI for content creation	7	0.768

Results

The response rate for the study was 100%. Total enumeration of 61 creative staff in advertising agencies in was carried out and all the copies of the instrument were filled, returned and validated. Analysis of data was carried out with the presentation of the quantitative analysis of variables, test of hypotheses, qualitative analysis of variables and discussion of findings with empirical literature.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 2: Level of Awareness of AI for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies

<i>Statements</i>	VH Freq. (%)	H Freq. (%)	L Freq. (%)	VL Freq. (%)	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation (SD)
Copy (Mean = 3.44, SD= 0.61)						
The level to which I am aware that AI can be used to generate scripts is ...	38 (62.3)	23 (37.7)	-	-	3.62	0.49
The level to which I am aware that AI can create personalized copy for different audience segments is...	29 (47.5%)	30 (49.2%)	1 (1.6)	1 (1.6)	3.43	0.62
The level to which I am aware that AI can translate scripts in foreign languages to local languages is ...	24 (39.3)	32 (52.5)	3 (4.9)	2 (3.3)	3.28	0.71
Visual (Mean = 3.34, SD= 0.66)						
The level to which I am aware that AI can create visually compelling content for advertising campaigns is ...	30 (49.2)	29 (47.5)	2 (3.3)	-	3.46	0.57
The level to which I am aware that AI can create visual content based on targeted user preferences is ...	30 (49.2)	28 (45.9)	3 (4.9)	-	3.44	0.59
The level to which I am aware that AI can edit videos for promotional purposes is ...	22 (36.1)	28 (45.9)	8 (13.1)	3 (4.9)	3.13	0.83
Audio (Mean = 3.10, SD= 0.86)						
The level to which I am aware that AI can generate voiceovers for promotional videos is ...	28 (45.9)	33 (54.1)	-	-	3.46	0.50
The level to which I am aware that AI can create jingles used in advertisements is ...	18 (29.5)	33 (54.1)	9 (14.8)	1 (1.6)	3.11	0.71
The level to which I am aware that AI can generate audio content in multiple languages is ...	14 (23)	26 (42.6)	11 (18)	10 (16.4)	2.72	1.00

Average Overall Mean					3.29	0.67
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*****Decision Rule if mean is 1 to 1.74=Very Low; 1.75 to 2.49 = Low; 2.50 to 3.24 =High; 3.25 to 4= Very High**

Table 2 shows that creatives in advertising agencies in Lagos State had very high level of awareness of the use of AI for content creation (\bar{x} =3.29). Creatives had higher level of awareness of the use of AI for copy (\bar{x} =3.44) and visual generation (\bar{x} =3.34) as opposed to audio generation (\bar{x} =3.10).

Table 3

Attitude towards AI for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies

<i>Statements</i>	SA Freq. (%)	A Freq. (%)	D Freq. (%)	SD Freq. (%)	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation (SD)
Copy (Mean = 3.35, SD= 0.58)						
I am open to collaborating with AI tools for copywriting	31 (50.8)	30 (49.2)	-	-	3.51	0.50
I believe AI can enhance the copywriting process	29 (47.5)	30 (49.2)	2 (3.3)	-	3.44	0.56
I believe AI can create efficient copies to target various audience segments	22 (36.1)	32 (52.5)	7 (11.5)	-	3.25	0.65
I believe using AI for copywriting can improve brand personality	18 (29.5)	36 (59)	7 (11.5)		3.18	0.62
Audio (Mean = 3.34, SD= 0.63)						
I believe AI can enhance audio creation processes	28 (45.9)	33 (54.1)	-	-	3.46	0.50
I am open to collaborating with AI tools for audio generation	28 (45.9)	32 (52.5)	1 (1.6)	-	3.44	0.53
I believe AI would help the creative process for audio generation	29 (47.5)	29 (47.5)	1 (1.6)	2 (3.3)	3.39	0.69
I believe AI can efficiently create audio content that appeals to a specific demographic	18 (29.5)	32 (52.5)	8 (13.1)	3 (4.9)	3.07	0.79
Visual (Mean = 3.14, SD= 0.67)						

I am open to collaborating with AI tools for visual content creation	26 (42.6)	33 (54.1)	2 (3.3)	-	3.39	0.56
I believe AI can enhance the process of creating visual content	21 (34.4)	39 (63.9)	1 (1.6)	-	3.33	0.51
I believe AI can enhance the artistic expressions in content creation	18 (29.5)	37 (60.7)	5 (8.2)	1 (1.6)	3.18	0.65
I believe AI can efficiently create visual content for promotional purposes	13 (21.3)	23 (37.7)	16 (26.2)	9 (14.8)	2.66	0.98
Average Overall Mean					3.28	0.63

*****Decision Rule if mean is 1 to 1.74=Strongly Disagree; 1.75 to 2.49 = Disagree; 2.50 to 3.24 =Agree; 3.25 to 4= Strongly Agree. Note: SA+A= Positive Perception; D+SD= Negative Perception**

Table 3 depicts creatives in advertising agencies in Lagos State generally had a positive attitude towards AI for content creation (\bar{x} =3.28). They specifically had positive attitude towards AI for copy (\bar{x} =3.35), audio (\bar{x} =3.34) and visual (\bar{x} =3.14) content creation.

Table 4

Extent of Adoption of AI for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies

<i>Statements</i>	VHE Freq. (%)	HE Freq. (%)	LE Freq. (%)	VLE Freq. (%)	Mean \bar{x}	Standard Deviation (SD)
Copy (Mean = 2.58, SD= 0.68)						
I use AI to generate scripts for this advertising agency	4 (6.6)	35 (57.4)	18 (29.5)	4 (6.6)	2.64	0.71
I use AI to create personalized copy for this advertising agency	-	40 (65.6)	18 (29.5)	3 (4.9)	2.61	0.59
I use AI to translate scripts in foreign languages for this advertising agency	3 (4.9)	29 (47.5)	23 (37.7)	6 (9.8)	2.48	0.74
Visual (Mean = 2.28, SD= 0.65)						
I use AI to generate posters for this advertising agency	1 (1.6)	36 (59)	18 (29.5)	6 (9.8)	2.52	0.70

I use AI to create videos for promotional purposes for this advertising agency	-	18 (29.5)	35 (57.4)	8 (13.1)	2.16	0.64
I use AI to edit video content for this advertising agency	-	16 (26.2)	38 (62.3)	7 (11.5)	2.15	0.60
Audio (Mean = 1.90, SD= 0.70)						
I use AI to create voiceovers for this advertising agency	-	18 (29.5)	30 (49.2)	13 (21.3)	2.08	0.71
I use AI to create jingles and music for this advertising agency	1 (1.6)	10 (16.4)	35 (57.4)	15 (24.6)	1.95	0.69
I use AI to create audio in a foreign language for this advertising agency	2 (3.3)	2 (3.3)	30 (49.2)	27 (44.3)	1.66	0.70
Average Overall Mean					2.25	0.68

*****Decision Rule if mean is 1 to 1.74=Very Low Extent; 1.75 to 2.49 = Low Extent; 2.50 to 3.24 =High Extent; 3.25 to 4= Very High Extent**

Table 4 shows that the extent of adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State was generally low (\bar{x} =2.25). However, the extent of adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in was high in respect of copy content creation (\bar{x} =2.58); where they used AI to: generate scripts (\bar{x} =2.64) and create personalized copy (\bar{x} =2.61). Conversely, the extent of adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in respect of visual (\bar{x} =2.28) and audio (\bar{x} =1.90) content creation was low.

Figure 3
Challenges Militating against AI Adoption for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies

Fig. 3 depicts that the most predominant challenges that were encountered in AI adoption were: data privacy (96.7%) and ethical (91.8%) concerns. Other challenges encountered were: expensive AI implementation (47.5%), lack of training resources for the use of AI for content creation (36.2%) and AI incompatibility with existing tools for content creation (24.6%).

Test of Hypotheses

Decision Rule

The following rules guided the application of simple linear regression for this study. If the p-value, which is the probability value, was less or equal to 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected; if p value was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted.

H01: Awareness of AI for content creation does not significantly influence attitude towards AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State.

Table 5

Influence of Awareness of AI for Content Creation on Attitude towards AI for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	p	R ²
(Constant)	19.667	4.541		4.331	.000	0.244
Awareness of AI for Content Creation	.662	.152	.494	4.367	.000	

Dependent Variable: Attitude towards AI for Content Creation

Note: β = Standardized Coefficient, significant at 0.05

Table 5 shows that awareness of AI for content creation positively significantly influenced attitude towards AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State ($R^2 = 0.244$, $\beta = 0.494$, $t(59) = 4.367$, $p < 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. This analysis suggests that improvement in awareness of AI for content creation would lead to positive attitudes towards AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State.

Ho2: Awareness of AI for content creation does not significantly influence adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State.

Table 6

Influence of Awareness of AI for Content Creation on Adoption of AI for Content Creation in Advertising Agencies

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	T	p	R ²
(Constant)	17.886	3.547		5.042	.000	0.008
<i>Awareness of AI for Content Creation</i>	.080	.118	.087	.672	.504	

Dependent Variable: Adoption of AI for Content Creation

Note: β = Standardized Coefficient, significant at 0.05

Table 6 depicts that awareness of AI for content creation had no significant influence on adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State ($R^2 = 0.008$, $\beta = 0.087$, $t(59) = 0.672$, $p > 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Analysis of Qualitative Data (In-depth Interview)

In-depth interviews were successfully conducted with ten management staff across advertising agencies in Lagos state. Interviewees requested anonymity for themselves as well as their organizations, hence in accordance with Heaton (2022), Elger and Caplan (2006) and Crow et al. (2006), the participants were assigned code names (P1, P2, P3, P4, ... P10). The analysis of the in-depth interviews is done by adopting themes from the research questions as follows:

What level of awareness do management staff and creatives of advertising agencies possess about AI for content creation?

The findings revealed that, while there is a general awareness of AI for content creation among management staff in advertising agencies in Lagos State, there is variation in the depth and extent of this awareness across management staff of advertising agencies in Lagos state. The majority of participants exhibited a moderate level of awareness, acknowledging the existence of AI tools and its application for content creation but lacking an in-depth knowledge of Artificial Intelligence capabilities. For instance, Participant P3 mentioned, "I am aware of artificial intelligence being used in content creation, but I am yet to understand how it works outside of Chatgpt and scriptwriting."

Conversely, a few participants demonstrated a high level of awareness, having a clear understanding of AI's role in content creation and its potential implications for advertising agencies. Participant P5 enunciated, "We've been exploring AI solutions for digital content creation to streamline our processes and improve efficiency within this agency." However, there were also instances of low awareness among some participants, particularly regarding the specific applications and benefits of AI in content creation. Participant P9 revealed, "I am aware of artificial intelligence but I haven't really looked into it for content creation. It's just something that has not seemed necessary at the moment."

What is the attitude of management staff and creatives of advertising agencies towards using AI for content creation?

The attitudes of management staff towards AI for content creation were diverse, ranging from enthusiasm and optimism to skepticism and apprehension. Majority of participants portrayed a positive attitude towards artificial intelligence and acknowledged it as a welcome technological advancement that could prove to be a vital tool for enhancing creativity, efficiency, and productivity within the advertising agencies and the process of content creation. Participant P5 stated, "I strongly believe AI has the potential to revolutionize how we approach content creation. It can help us generate ideas faster and produce content more efficiently and meet deadlines which is a bonus not just for us but will satisfy our clients." Participants P1, P2, P4, P8 and P10 also agreed that artificial Intelligence has a lot of potential benefits including time efficiency, research, idea generation and accuracy. Participant P7 elaborates and states that "there is a lot AI can do especially with targeted campaigns and making content specifically for a particular segment of the audience" This refers to the ability of artificial intelligence to aid "personalization" as corroborated by Participant P1. Participant P2 expresses that "If you do not evolve, you will go extinct just like the dinosaur", this denotes that in order to not be left behind with changing times there is a need to develop and hop on digital trends. Participant P5 and P2 also accord a degree of their readiness to integrate artificial intelligence to be due to its adoption by "global industry partners" who they collaborate with in order to expand and get opportunities internationally.

Additionally, there were participants who adopted a neutral stance towards AI for content creation, acknowledging its potential benefits but also recognizing the need for careful consideration and oversight in its implementation. Participant P8 stated, "I see AI as a tool that can enhance our creative process, but we need to ensure it is in line with our agency's values and objectives." Speaking on the organizational policies and how it impacts the decision of if or not AI is integrated, Participant P1 stated that the agency adopts an "IT Governance policy" which ensures that the pros and cons of adopting any new technology is weighed before integration can occur. Participant P7 voiced that the agency allows room for the creatives to have "individual experimentation". This suggests that creatives are encouraged to explore and seek to develop with changing times and use whatever tools are at their disposal "as long as it does not affect authenticity."

In contrast, there were participants who harbored reservations regarding the integration of AI in content creation, expressing concerns about its impact on job security, creativity, and the lack of authenticity of content. Participant P3 stated, "I'm very hesitant to integrate AI into our work process. I fear getting to rely on it might diminish the human element of storytelling which we pride ourselves on and it can lead to very generic, uninspired content."

What is the extent of adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State?

There was notable variation in the degree of adoption across advertising agencies, with some agencies embracing AI technologies while others remained hesitant or resistant to its integration. Majority of the participants indicated that their agencies had begun experimenting with AI tools for content creation, albeit on a limited scale. Participant P4 mentioned, "We've started incorporating AI-powered software for tasks like script writing and developing graphics, but it's still in the early stages." Other participants also indicated integration of AI into their creation processes and attributing the limited scale of adoption to the fact that AI is in its "beta phase", in agreement with this Participant P2 categorically asserts that "where AI is right now is not even a fraction of what we would see as it continues to develop" Participant P10 mentioned that although

the agency had begun integrating it, a major factor to be considered was its “scalability” stating that the AI powered solutions they prioritize must be able to handle large data sets which would otherwise cost the agency time and other resources to get through.

In contrast, there were participants whose agencies had yet to explore AI for content creation, citing factors such as budget constraints, lack of sufficient training, and concerns about its ethical implications as well as its effect on the creativity of staff. Participant P3 shared apprehension on over reliance on the technology and shared a past experience with a staff using AI to create very generic posters for a client and caused a setback for the agency, he further explains that when given such room “lazy staff” take advantage of it and it would impede on the creativity their clients expect to get.

However, a few participants highlighted instances of successful implementation of AI in content creation within their agencies, showcasing a higher level of adoption. Participant P5 shared, “We’ve fully integrated AI into our content creation processes, from idea generation to editing. It has significantly enhanced our efficiency and output quality.” Participants P1, P6, P7 and P10 also indicated a higher level of adoption of AI for content creation across copywriting, visual and audio content creation, citing specific AI powered tools like Google Gemini, Slide Creator, Midjourney, Prompt Creator, Dall-E, Microsoft Azure and Elementor by Wordpress. Participants also noted that a lot of the existing tools they utilize for content creation have begun to integrate some AI features into their software like Canva and Adobe.

What are the challenges that are encountered in the adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies?

A major recurring challenge was data privacy and security risks and the ethical considerations associated with the adoption of AI tools for content creation. Participant P10 emphasized, “Ensuring the security and confidentiality of our data when using AI tools is a top priority. There has to be some certainty that our intellectual property would not be compromised.” Furthermore, participants raised concerns about the difficulty in finding AI tools that align with the specific needs of the agency. Participant P8 stated, “Getting AI tools that cater to our content requirements has been a struggle. Many options seem too generic and that is not what we are looking out for.” In line with this Participant P6 also noted that a lot of the accessible AI tools at their disposal are not equipped to fit into the Nigerian local content scene. This sheds light on the limitation of AI-tools to localize audio content, particularly in languages or dialects with regional nuances or accents. This suggests that although AI has made significant strides in text-based content generation and translation, the complexities of accent recognition, dialect interpretation, and cultural nuances presents a great challenge in audio localization.

Another significant challenge highlighted by participants was the reluctance from team members towards embracing AI for content creation. Participants expressed concerns about job displacement, loss of creative control, and the perceived threat to their roles. Contrarily, a few participants strongly believe that artificial intelligence “will never not even in twenty years replace human creativity” as asserted by Participant P4. Supporting this school of thought, Participant P2 states that artificial intelligence is not going to take away the creativity that only humans are blessed with and are capable of having. Participant P7 contributes to this by stating that in order to use these AI powered tools, one must first possess a “repository of knowledge to be able to dish out prompts”, this suggests that the output of AI is only as good as the input or the prompt which you give to it or “garbage in, garbage out” as Participant P5 puts it. Participant P9 sums it up thus “AI tries to imitate and replicate but cannot on its own create, artists have the ability to create and

that is a major distinction that would continue to be a selling point for creatives in the industry. AI is a vehicle whose performance depends largely on the skill of the driver.” Additionally, participants noted the resource-intensive nature of integrating AI into existing content creation processes, including the need for specialized training, infrastructure upgrades, and ongoing maintenance costs. Participant P3 stated, "Adopting AI for content creation requires a significant investment in terms of time, money, and expertise. It's not something we can rush into without careful planning and consideration."

Discussion of Findings

The findings are consistent with the assumptions of TAM and S-O-R Model and demonstrated that perception of the efficiency and usefulness of AI derived from awareness of its capabilities to enhance productivity and creativity within the advertising industry could positively stimulate the attitudes towards AI and affect their adoption decisions. Additionally, the Stimuli-Organism-Response model emphasizes on the role of environmental factors in shaping behavioral responses, these include organizational support and culture, industry trends and the global partners' initiatives.

The current study found that efforts geared towards the increase in awareness of artificial intelligence as a content creation tool would positively influence attitudinal disposition towards AI. These efforts have been found to have a favorable effect on people's views toward artificial intelligence (AI), indicating that raising knowledge through education can encourage people to be more open to adopting AI. The significance of focused awareness efforts and training programs within advertising firms to improve comprehension and adoption of AI technologies for content generation is emphasized by the study by Murar and Kubovics (2023). Notably, while majority of participants expressed excitement, receptiveness and an openness to collaboration, some management staff of advertising agencies displayed skepticism, apprehension, towards AI as a content creation tool owing to their concerns on privacy and security, scalability, budget implications of integrating AI and ethical concerns.

Corroboratively, Leszczynski et al., (2022) found that the attitudes of respondents varied largely owing to the potential challenges in its use as well as the concerns of the managers of advertising agencies. Similarly, Jeffery (2021) found that Generation Z generally expressed a positive attitude towards AI generated content, however they also expressed worries about privacy, stereotyping, and manipulation. Building on these, Burlacu (2023) identified the lack of the human emotional sense in artificial intelligence generated content, limitations in personalization, repetitive and generic content as well as privacy and security challenges. Wernersson and Persson (2023) showed that creatives were resistant to adopting artificial intelligence as a response to the fear of AI replacing humans and job loss, the respondents also raised ethical concerns especially copyright issues as a challenge in the adoption of artificial intelligence.

Moreover, findings affirmed that awareness of AI for content creation does not significantly influence the adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos. This implies that although awareness plays a significant role in influencing people's views toward AI, adoption decisions in organizational settings are not solely determined by awareness. Rather, other factors like organizational preparedness, resource availability, perceived utility, and workflow compatibility as implied in the study by Zerfass et al., (2020), have an impact on the adoption of

AI for content creation. This emphasizes the necessity of a comprehensive strategy to encourage the adoption of AI in advertising companies. In order to solve the difficulties that agencies encounter when incorporating AI technologies into their operations, adoption promotion efforts should go beyond projects aimed at raising awareness. Agencies may improve their readiness for AI adoption and take advantage of the potential advantages AI presents for industry innovation and content production by addressing these more general aspects.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings of the study portray artificial intelligence (AI) as a formidable tool for content creation on an organizational scale. Drawing from the findings of the study it can be concluded that awareness of AI for content creation is not a major determinant for adoption of AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State. Additionally, awareness of AI for content creation positively significantly influences attitude towards AI for content creation in advertising agencies in Lagos State. It was also concluded that the level of adoption of AI for content creation was generally low in advertising agencies in Lagos State. The study therefore recommends that efforts towards increasing awareness on AI be intensified to create a positive atmosphere for integration. Additionally, advertising agencies should prioritize training and continuous personal development so as to build an environment that can foster a culture of innovation and experimentation among creative.

Conflicts of Interest

The author has disclosed no conflicts of interest.

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REFERENCES

- Albrighton, T. (2013) The ABC of Copywriting. <https://www.abccopywriting.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/The-ABC-of-Copywriting.pdf>
- Arias-Badia, B., and Matamala, A. (2020). Audio description meets Easy-to-Read and Plain Language: Results from a questionnaire and a focus group in Catalonia. *Journal for Cultural Techniques and Cultural Sciences*, 251-270. <https://doi.org/10.46586/ZfK.2020.251-270>.
- Burlacu, C. (2023). The Impact of AI-Powered Content Generation on Customer Experience.
- Chandra, S., Verma, S., Lim, W. M., Kumar, S., & Donthu, N. (2022). Personalization in personalized marketing: Trends and ways forward. *Psychology & Marketing*, 39(11), 2165-2181. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.21670>
- Chan-Olmsted, S. M. (2019). A Review of Artificial Intelligence Adoptions in the Media Industry. *International Journal on Media Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14241277.2019.1695619>.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- Gerzic, A., and Abou Osman, A. (2017). Content creation activities related to content marketing through social media: A qualitative study in a B2B context.
- Ivanov, S. (2023). Using Artificial Intelligence to Create Marketing Content – Opportunities and Limitations.
- Jeffrey, T. R. (2021). Understanding Generation Z Perceptions of Artificial Intelligence in Marketing and Advertising. *Advertising and Society Quarterly*, 22(4). <https://doi.org/10.1353/asr.2021.0052>.
- Leszczynski, G., Salamon, K., and Zieliński, M. (2022). Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence in Advertising Agencies.
- Mehrabian, A., & Russell, J. A. (1974). An approach to environmental psychology. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press`
- Murár, P., and Kubovics, M. (2023). Using AI to Create Content Designed for Marketing Communications. *European Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 18, 660-668. <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecie.18.1.1638>
- Nwachukwu, D., & Affen, M. (2023). Artificial Intelligence Marketing Practices: The Way Forward to Better Customer Experience Management in Africa (Systematic Literature Review). 9, 44-62.
- Patrick, V. M., and Hagtvedt, H. (2011). Advertising Visuals. *Art in Advertising*. In *Encyclopedia of Creativity*. San Diego: 18-23.
- Rehm, G. (2020). *Research for CULT Committee - The use of Artificial Intelligence in the Audiovisual Sector*.
- Shamsuddin, F., Rahamad, M. S., and Hasmah. (2023). Challenges of creative development by advertising industry players in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Applied Communication*, 12(1). e-ISSN: 2682-7506
- Shehata, M. M. A., Awad, H. M., and Gebba, N. A. E. R. (2020). Philosophy of the Visual Metaphor in the Advertising Poster Design. *Mansoura Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 11(8), 1537-1553. <https://doi.org/10.21608/mjaf.2020.25455.1537>.
- Sheikh, H., Prins, C., and Schrijvers, E. (2023). Artificial Intelligence: Definition and Background.

- In *Mission AI: Research for Policy* (pp. 15-28). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21448-6_2
- Wernersson, J., and Persson, R. (2023). Exploring the Potential Impact of AI on the Role of Graphic Content Creators: Benefits, Challenges, and Collaborative Opportunities.
- Yang, Q., Qin, L., Chen, Z., Ji, S., Zhang, K., and Ma, X. (2019). *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, Volume 91, 1st International Symposium on Economic Development and Management Innovation (EDMI 2019), Empirical Study on the Impact of Short Video Content Marketing on Consumer's Purchasing Intention based on the Integrated Model of TRA and ELM. <https://doi.org/10.2991/edmi-19.2019.86>
- Zerfass, A., Hagelstein, J., and Tench, R. (2020). Artificial intelligence in communication management: A cross-national study on adoption and knowledge, impact, challenges, and risks. *Journal of Communication Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCOM-10-2019-0137>
- Zia, A., Javed, N., and Bilal, M. (2018). Copywriting Elements and Brand Relationship: An Analysis of Print Advertisements' Language. *Global Social Sciences Review*, III, 410-430. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2018\(III-III\).23](https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2018(III-III).23).